

In order to describe complexation qualitatively a plot of $\log K_n$ vs $f(\bar{n}-1)$ has been drawn (Fig. 1). The higher values of K_1 and K_3 compared with

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log K_n$ vs $(\bar{n}-1)$.

K_1 primarily reflects the presence of two possible structures, competing with each other. The tendency to form more stable structure (i.e. tetrahedral ones) is evident at ca. $\bar{n}=3$ (Fig. 1). A sudden break indicates the conversion of stabler form into less stable structure which could have been observed at higher coordination number.

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Effect of Ionic Surfactants on the Chromatographic Separation of Phenols

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RECENTLY, the use of micellar systems in analytical techniques have been reviewed¹. However, the use of surfactants has not been tried so far to study the movement of phenols on chro-

matographic papers. In this study we have made use of aqueous micellar (normal micellar) systems of different charge type in the separation of phenols. It is well known that the properties of micelles are drastically changed by the change of environment, hence the effect of alcohols and salts has been studied on the separation of phenols in the presence of such additives in the micellar systems

This paper deals with the paper chromatography of 28 phenols of different types in aqueous sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) systems. The effect of addition of propanol and electrolytes (NaCl and KBr) is also studied. The important separations, practically achieved, are reported.

Experimental

Chromatography was performed on Whatman No. 3 paper strips of size 15×3 cm using 20×5 cm glass jars.

Chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) were B. D. H. (England) products, which were further purified by repeated crystallisation from 95% ethanol followed by prolonged extraction from chloroform (100 h) and petroleum ether (60 h) to ensure the complete removal of traces of unreacted alcohol. It was then filtered and dried overnight in an hot air-oven to a constant weight. The purity of the surfactants was ensured from the absence of minimum in the surface tension vs concentration plots. The spotting solutions of phenols were prepared in ethanol. For the detection of various phenols, ferric chloride solution (0.1 M), sodium hydroxide solution (0.1 M) and 1% phosphomolybdic acid solution were used.

Procedure: Phenols were spotted with the help of fine glass capillaries on the strips. The paper was conditioned for 15 min and solvent was then allowed to ascend 11 cm in every case. The R_f values were calculated as usual.

Results

Detection: Phenols were easily detected on chromatograms. For the detection of various phenols, ferric chloride sodium hydroxide and phosphomolybdic acids were used. The variety of colours obtained with various types of phenols are as follows.

Phloroglucinol, catechol, xylenol, bromothymol blue, di(2-hydroxyphenylimino)ethane gave blue coloured spots.

In certain cases the use of sodium hydroxide spray was also made just after spraying ferric chloride to achieve clear detection. The colours observed with known phenols are as follows. *m*-Cresol and *p*-cresol gave brown spots. Resorcinol and gallic acid gave violet spots. 1-Nitroso-2-naphthol gave green spot. Pyrogallol gave blue spot.

8-Hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline-5-sulphonic acid and phenyl fluorone (9-phenyl-2,3,7-trihydroxy-6-fluorone) gave wine-red spots. *o*-Nitrophenol and picric acid gave yellow spots. Trihydroxy-6-fluorone and bromocresol green gave blue spots. Phenolphthalein gave pink spot. However, with some phenols where ferric chloride did not give satisfactory detection, the use of phosphomolybdic acid was made. The use of sodium hydroxide spray was also made just after spraying phosphomolybdic acid to achieve clear and quick detection. α -Naphthol, β -naphthol, *p*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 1,2,5,8-anthroxanthraquinone, 4-chlorophenol and phenol gave blue spots. Quinol gave brown spots.

Chromatography: R_f values of the following 23 phenols in water and different concentrations of SDS and CTAB were calculated. Phenols studied were phloroglucinol, α -naphthol, β -naphthol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, *p*-nitrophenol, catechol, *m*-cresol, *p*-cresol, phenol, resorcinol, gallic acid, *o*-nitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, xylenol, quinol, picric acid, vanilline, pyrogallol, bromothymol blue, 1,2,5,8-anthroxanthraquinone, 4-(4-nitrophenyl)azoresorcinol, di(2-hydroxyphenylimino)ethane, 8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline-5-sulphonic acid, phenylfluorone (9-phenyl-2,3,7-trihydroxy-6-fluorone), trihydroxy-6-fluorone, 4-chlorophenol, bromocresol green, phenolphthalein.

The various solvent systems were (i) aqueous SDS system: 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 mM L⁻¹ SDS; (ii) aqueous CTAB system: 0.1, 0.5, 0.7, 1.0 and 1.5 mM L⁻¹ CTAB; (iii) 2, 4, 6 and 8% propanol with SDS systems: 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 mM L⁻¹ SDS; (iv) 2, 4, 6 and 8% propanol with CTAB systems: 0.1, 0.5, 0.7, 1.0 and 1.5 mM L⁻¹ CTAB; (v) 0.25, 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M NaCl with SDS systems: 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 mM L⁻¹ SDS, (vi) 0.025, 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M KBr with CTAB systems: 0.1, 0.5, 0.7, 1.0 and 1.5 mM L⁻¹ CTAB.

The effect of propanol was studied on the movement of phenols in SDS and CTAB systems. The solutions of SDS and CTAB were prepared in propanol + water.

It is well known that the addition of electrolytes in the aqueous surfactant solution affects their properties. Aqueous micellar systems as such and in the presence of additives may influence the movement of phenols during the separation, hence various concentrations of sodium chloride and potassium bromide were added in the SDS and CTAB solution, respectively. These electrolytes were taken just as the representatives of the normal salts.

Separation: On the basis of difference in R_f values of phenols some analytically important separations were tried and those achieved practically are categorised as binary and ternary separations. The R_f values are given in parenthesis.

Binary separations of phenols achieved in 8% propanol with 8 mM L⁻¹ SDS are as follows:

(i) phloroglucinol (0.91) from α -naphthol (0.46), β -naphthol (0.50), 2,4-dinitrophenol (0.46), *o*-nitrophenol (0.16), 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (0.58), vanilline (0.71), 1, 2, 5, 8-anthroxanthraquinone (0.00), pyrogallol (0.67), di(2-hydroxyphenylimino)ethane (0.11), phenylfluorone (9-phenyl-2, 3, 7-trihydroxy-6-fluorone) (0.00); (ii) α -naphthol (0.46) from *p*-nitrophenol (0.71), catechol (0.95), *m*-cresol (0.95), *p*-cresol (0.78), phenol (0.89), resorcinol (0.65), gallic acid (0.73), quinol (0.72), picric acid (0.76), 4-chlorophenol (0.71), pyrogallol (0.67); (iii) β -naphthol (0.50) from *p*-nitrophenol (0.71), catechol (0.95), *m*-cresol (0.95), *p*-cresol (0.78), phenol (0.89), xylenol (0.95), picric acid (0.76), thymol blue (0.98), phenolphthalein (0.78); (iv) 2,4-dinitrophenol (0.46) from catechol (0.95), *p*-nitrophenol (0.71), phenol (0.89), xylenol (0.95), picric acid (0.76), bromothymol blue (0.98), bromocresol green (0.92); (v) *p*-nitrophenol (0.71) from *o*-nitrophenol (0.16), xylenol (0.95), 4,4-nitrophenylazoresorcinol (0.80), bromocresol green (0.92); (vi) catechol (0.95) from *o*-nitrophenol (0.16), 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (0.58), 4-(4-nitrophenyl)azoresorcinol (0.08); (vii) *m*-cresol (0.95) from *o*-nitrophenol (0.16), 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (0.58); (viii) *p*-cresol (0.78) from *o*-nitrophenol (0.16), di(2-hydroxyphenylimino)ethane (0.11); (ix) phenol (0.89) from vanilline (0.71), *o*-nitrophenol (0.16); (x) resorcinol (0.65) from bromothymol blue (0.98), di(2-hydroxyphenylimino)ethane (0.11); (xi) gallic acid (0.73) from xylenol (0.95); (xii) *o*-nitrophenol (0.16) from quinol (0.72), picric acid (0.76), pyrogallol (0.67); (xiii) 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (0.58) from picric acid (0.76); (xiv) xylenol (0.95) from vanilline (0.71), quinol (0.72); (xv) picric acid (0.76) from 1,2,5,8-anthroxanthraquinone (0.00), 4-(4-nitrophenyl)azoresorcinol (0.08); (xvi) vanilline (0.71) from bromothymol blue (0.98); (xvii) 4-chlorophenol (0.71) from bromocresol green (0.92).

Ternary separations of phenols achieved in 8% propanol with 8 mM L⁻¹ SDS are as follows: (i) phloroglucinol (0.91) and β -naphthol (0.50) from *p*-nitrophenol; (ii) 2,4-dinitrophenol (0.46) and *p*-nitrophenol (0.71) from *o*-nitrophenol (0.16); (iii) picric acid (0.76) and *o*-nitrophenol (0.16) from 2,4-dinitrophenol (0.46); (iv) *m*-cresol (0.95) and gallic acid (0.73) from 1, 2, 5, 8-anthroxanthraquinone; (v) phenol (0.89) and α -naphthol (0.46) from 4-(4-nitrophenyl)azoresorcinol (0.08); (vi) *p*-nitrophenol (0.71) and *o*-nitrophenol (0.16) from 4-(4-nitrophenyl)azoresorcinol (0.08).

Discussion

The results of this study reveal that the nature of the solvent system differs considerably for the movement of various phenol. Use has been made of different solvent systems with variation in concentration and ratio of surfactants as well as that of the electrolytes. The results reveals that the R_f values of phenols are not much more affected by the higher concentration of added electrolytes (Fig. 1).

However, the selectivity is increased by the addition of surfactants.

Fig. 1. Effect of SDS concentration on R_f value of α -naphthol in various concentration of NaCl: (O) NaCl, (Δ) 2, ($\square$) 4, ($\times$) 6, ($\bullet$) 8 and ($\blacktriangle$) 10 $mM L^{-1}$ SDS.

The chromatography of phenol in these systems show differential selectivity which gives the differentiation of the R_f values, as a result the separation of isomeric phenols, e.g. *o*-nitrophenol from *p*-nitrophenol has been achieved. Various other important separations (binary and ternary) have been achieved in about 0.5 h using 8% propanol with 8 $mM L^{-1}$ SDS system as mobile phase.

The separations are quick and distinct zones are obtained on the paper (Fig. 2). The results show that a variety of aqueous micellar systems can be applied as mobile phase for interested separations.

Fig. 2. Separations achieved in 8 $mM L^{-1}$ SDS: (Ia) phloroglucinol, (Ib) α -naphthol, (IIa) picric acid, (IIb) 2,4-dinitrophenol, (IIIa) *p*-nitrophenol, (IIIb) *o*-nitrophenol, (IVa) picric acid, (IVb) 2,4-dinitrophenol and (IVc) *o*-nitrophenol.

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Cycloalkanes. Part-IV. Friedel-Crafts Condensation of *cis*-Cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic Acid Anhydride with Aromatic Compounds and Synthesis of Simple and Substituted 2,3-Tetramethylene-5,6-benzcyclohexanes

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THE Friedel and Crafts condensation between phthalic anhydride and simple, substituted and polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons has been reported^{1,2} in a bid to synthesise anthracene derivatives. However, no attempts have so far been made to condense *cis*-cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid anhydride with aromatic hydrocarbons under Friedel-Crafts reaction conditions. We now report here the synthesis of simple and substituted 2,3-tetramethylene-5,6-benzcyclohexanes. The anhydride of *cis*-cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid was

condensed separately with benzene, toluene and anisole in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to give the corresponding 2-arylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acids (1a-c) which were characterised by ir and tlc. These acids when reduced by Wolff-Kishner method³ gave the corresponding 2-aryl-cyclohexane-1-carboxylic acids (2a-c) which were then converted into their chlorides by reaction with thionyl chloride. These acid chlorides when subjected to internal Friedel-Crafts reaction⁴ furnished the corresponding cyclic ketones (3a-c) which on subsequent Wolff-Kishner reduction yielded the desired hydrocarbons (4a-c) (Table 1).